

**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP1.SOP5 – DNA extraction
from soil and faeces
Workpackage 1**

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DNA EXTRACTION FROM SOIL AND FAECES

Protocol 1: Isolation of DNA from soil using FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals Catalogue number: 116560200)

Note: This protocol requires a FastPrep or equivalent bead-beating instrument

1	Add up to 500 mg of soil sample to a Lysing Matrix E tube. <ul style="list-style-type: none">The manufacturer recommends using up to 500 mg of most soil types. Very wet soils or detritus-rich soils may require less sample by mass.
2	Add 978 μ L Sodium Phosphate Buffer to sample in Lysing Matrix E tube.
3	Add 122 μ L MT Buffer. <ul style="list-style-type: none">The fill volume of the lysing matrix tube after addition of Sodium Phosphate and MT Buffers to the sample should allow sufficient air space in the sample tube for efficient FastPrep instrument processing.
4	Homogenize in the FastPrep instrument for 40 seconds at a speed setting of 6.0.
5	Centrifuge at 14,000 x g for 5-10 minutes to pellet debris. <ul style="list-style-type: none">Note: Extending centrifugation to 15 minutes can enhance elimination of excessive debris from large samples or from cells with complex cell walls.
6	Transfer supernatant to a clean 2.0 mL microcentrifuge tube. Add 250 μ L PPS (Protein Precipitation Solution) and mix by inverting the tube 10 times.
7	Centrifuge at 14,000 x g for 5 minutes to pellet precipitate. Transfer supernatant to a clean 15 mL microcentrifuge tube. <ul style="list-style-type: none">Note: While a 2.0 mL microcentrifuge tube may be used at this step, more efficient mixing and DNA binding will occur in a larger tube.
8	Resuspend the Binding Matrix suspension and add 1.0 mL to the supernatant in the 15 mL tube.
9	Place on rotator or invert by hand for 2 minutes to allow binding of DNA. Place tube on a rack for 3 minutes to allow settling of silica matrix.
10	Remove and discard 500 μ L of supernatant being careful to avoid settled Binding Matrix.
11	Gently re-suspend Binding Matrix in the remaining amount of supernatant. Transfer approximately 600 μ L of the mixture to a SPIN™ filter and centrifuge at 14,000 x g for 1 minute. Empty the catch tube and add the remaining mixture to the SPIN Filter and centrifuge as before. Empty the catch tube again.
12	Add 500 μ L prepared SEWS-M and gently re-suspend the pellet using the force of the liquid from the pipet tip.
13	Centrifuge at 14,000 x g for 1 minute. Empty the catch tube and replace.
14	Without addition of any liquid, centrifuge a second time at 14,000 x g for 2 minutes to “dry” the matrix of residual wash solution. Discard the catch tube with a new, clean catch tube.
15	Air dry the SPIN Filter for 5 minutes at room temperature.

16	<p>Gently resuspend Binding Matrix (above the SPIN Filter) in 50 - 100 μL of DES (DNase/Pyrogen-Free Water).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: To avoid over-dilution of the purified DNA, use smallest amount of DES required to re-suspend Binding Matrix pellet• Note: Yields may be increased by incubation for 5 minutes at 55°C in a heat block or water bath.
17	<p>Centrifuge at 14,000 x g for 1 minute to bring eluted DNA into the clean catch tube. Discard the SPIN Filter. DNA is now ready for PCR and other downstream applications. Store at -20°C for extended periods or 4°C until use.</p>

Protocol 2: Isolation of DNA from soil using Qiagen DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen Catalogue number: 47014/47016)

Note: This protocol requires a Vortex adapter for vortexing 1.5 ml/2 ml tubes. Alternatively, a bead-beating instrument can be used.

1	<p>Spin the PowerBead Pro Tube briefly to ensure that the beads have settled at the bottom. Add up to 250 mg of soil and 800 μl of Solution CD1. Vortex briefly to mix.</p>
2	<p>Secure the PowerBead Pro Tube horizontally on a Vortex adapter for 1.5–2 ml tubes. Vortex at maximum speed for 10 min.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: If using the Vortex adapter for more than 12 preps simultaneously, increase the vortexing time by 5–10 min.• Note: For alternative ways to homogenize samples, see the manufacturer's protocol.
3	<p>Centrifuge the PowerBead Pro Tube at 15,000 x g for 1 min.</p>
4	<p>Transfer the supernatant to a clean 2 ml micro-centrifuge tube.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: Expect 500–600 μl. The supernatant may still contain some soil particles.
5	<p>Add 200 μl of Solution CD2 and vortex for 5 s.</p>
6	<p>Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 min. Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to 700 μl of supernatant to a clean 2 ml micro-centrifuge tube.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: Expect 500–600 μl.
7	<p>Add 600 μl of Solution CD3 and vortex for 5 s.</p>
8	<p>Load 650 μl of lysate to an MB Spin Column. Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 min.</p>
9	<p>Discard the flow-through and repeat step 8 to ensure that all of the lysate has passed through the MB Spin Column.</p>
10	<p>Carefully place the MB Spin Column into a clean 2 ml collection tube. Avoid splashing any flow-through onto the MB Spin Column.</p>
11	<p>Add 500 μl of Solution EA to the MB Spin Column. Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 min.</p>

12	Discard the flow-through and place the MB Spin Column back into the same 2 ml collection tube.
13	Add 500 µl of Solution C5 to the MB Spin Column. Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 min.
14	Discard the flow-through and place the MB Spin Column into a new 2 ml Collection Tube.
15	Centrifuge at up to 16,000 x g for 2 min. Carefully place the MB Spin Column into a new 1.5 ml Elution Tube
16	Add 50–100 µl of Solution C6 to the centre of the white filter membrane.
17	Centrifuge at 15,000 x g for 1 min. Discard the MB Spin Column. The DNA is now ready for downstream applications. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: It is recommend to store the DNA frozen (–30°C to –15°C or –90°C to –65°C) as Solution C6 does not contain EDTA.

Protocol 3: Isolation of DNA from faeces using QIAamp Fast DNA Stool Mini Kit (Qiagen Catalogue number: 51604)

1	Weigh 180–220 mg stool in a 2 ml microcentrifuge tube (not provided) and place tube on ice. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• This protocol is optimized for use with 180–220 mg stool but can also be used with smaller amounts. There is no need to reduce the amounts of buffers when using smaller amounts of stool.• If the sample is liquid, pipet 200 µl into the microcentrifuge tube. Cut the end of the pipet tip to make pipetting easier.
2	Add 1 ml InhibitEX Buffer to each stool sample. Vortex continuously for 1 min or until the stool sample is thoroughly homogenized. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: It is important to vortex the samples thoroughly. This helps ensure maximum DNA concentration in the final eluate.
3	Heat the suspension for 5 min at 70°C. Vortex for 15 s. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• This heating step helps to lyse bacteria and other parasites. The lysis temperature can be increased to 95°C for cells that are difficult to lyse (such as Gram-positive bacteria).
4	Centrifuge sample at full speed for 1 min to pellet stool particles. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• IMPORTANT: Do not transfer any solid material. If particles are still visible in the supernatant, centrifuge the sample again.
5	Pipet 15 µl proteinase K into a new 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube.
6	Pipet 200 µl supernatant from step 4 into the 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube containing proteinase K.
7	Add 200 µl Buffer AL and vortex for 15 s. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: Do not add proteinase K directly to Buffer AL. It is essential that the sample and Buffer AL are thoroughly mixed to form a homogeneous solution.

8	Incubate at 70°C for 10 min. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Centrifuge briefly to remove drops from the inside of the tube lid.
9	Add 200 µl of ethanol (96–100%) to the lysate, and mix by vortexing. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Centrifuge briefly to remove drops from the inside of the tube lid.
10	Carefully apply 600 µl lysate from step 9 to the QIAamp spin column. Close the cap and centrifuge at full speed for 1 min. Place the QIAamp spin column in a new 2 ml collection tube, and discard the tube containing the filtrate. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Close each spin column to avoid aerosol formation during centrifugation. If the lysate has not completely passed through the column after centrifugation, centrifuge again until the QIAamp spin column is empty.
11	Carefully open the QIAamp spin column and add 500 µl Buffer AW1. Centrifuge at full speed for 1 min. Place the QIAamp spin column in a new 2 ml collection tube, and discard the collection tube containing the filtrate.
12	Carefully open the QIAamp spin column and add 500 µl Buffer AW2. Centrifuge at full speed for 3 min. Discard the collection tube containing the filtrate. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: Residual Buffer AW2 in the eluate may cause problems in downstream applications. Some centrifuge rotors may vibrate upon deceleration, causing the flowthrough containing Buffer AW2 to come in contact with the QIAamp spin column.• Removing the QIAamp spin column and collection tube from the rotor may also cause flow-through to come into contact with the QIAamp spin column.
13	Place the QIAamp spin column in a new 2 ml collection tube and discard the old collection tube with the filtrate. Centrifuge at full speed for 3 min. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• This step helps to eliminate the chance of possible Buffer AW2 carryover.
14	Transfer the QIAamp spin column into a new, labeled 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube and pipet 200 µl Buffer ATE directly onto the QIAamp membrane. Incubate for 1 min at room temperature, then centrifuge at full speed for 1 min to elute DNA.

Protocol 3A: Isolation of DNA from larger volumes of faeces using QIAamp Fast DNA Stool Mini Kit (Qiagen Catalogue number: 51604)

1	Weigh the stool sample and add 10 volumes of InhibitEx Buffer (e.g., add 10 ml InhibitEx buffer to 1 g stool).
2	Vortex continuously for 1 min or until the stool sample is thoroughly homogenized. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Note: It is important to vortex the samples thoroughly. This helps ensure maximum DNA concentration in the final eluate.
3	Pipet 2 ml of lysate into a labeled 2 ml microcentrifuge tube. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cut the ends off the pipet tips to make pipetting viscous samples easier.
4	Continue from step 4 above.